

Hydrolysis of Casein by Immobilised Pepsin on Egg Shells and Synthetic Zeolites

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Manuscript received 28 February 1994, revised 13 July 1994, accepted 8 November 1994

Pepsin has been immobilised by covalent binding on egg shells using crosslinking agent glutaraldehyde, and physically adsorbed on synthetic zeolites. The covalently immobilised pepsin possess high retention of activity and high stability at high temperature and extreme pH than the pepsin adsorbed on zeolites. The native and immobilised pepsin preparations are characterised in terms of the activity, thermal stability, pH, temperature optima and kinetic constants.

Immobilised enzymes have great potential in chemical and food industry due to their high stability and reusability¹. Immobilisation of enzymes can be an useful strategy both to improve catalyst properties for biotechnological use² and also to study the kinetic behaviour and reaction mechanism³. The use of pepsin as biocatalyst is an area of active research owing to its simple mode of action and its application in cheese production. Nitschmann and Bohren⁴ made first attempt to study the kinetics of the hydrolysis of casein by enzyme chymosin. There has been a large scale search for an acceptable substitute of chymosin. Protease from animals (pepsin) have been tried. Being both a protein and a proteolytic enzyme, pepsin is capable of digesting itself⁵. Autodigestion of pepsin can be prevented by immobilising it.

Very little detailed study was done regarding immobilisation of pepsin and kinetics of action of pepsin. The methods include pepsin immobilised on DEAE cellulose⁶, *p*-amino-D-L-phenylalanine-L-leucine⁷ and polyaminopolystyrene⁸. The substrate is either haemoglobin or *N*-acetylphenyl-2,5-diiodotyrosine (APDT) in all the above cases. These methods of immobilisation are time-consuming, uneconomical and lead to increase in reaction volume. Hence, we chose immobilised supports as egg shells and zeolites, being easily available and cheap. The present paper emphasises preparation and kinetics of native and immobilised pepsin complexes and a comparative study.

JICS-5

Results and Discussion

The activity of pepsin immobilised on egg shells of 50, 80 and 100 mesh was found to be 20, 31 and 40% respectively, of that of native enzyme. The higher activity on 100 mesh size was attributed to exposure of more surface area for binding of enzyme. Further higher mesh size particles were not used because of their tendency to float on the surface of the reaction mixture. The activity of pepsin immobilised on synthetic zeolites with 5Å, 13Å and 100 mesh size was found to be 10, 65 and 80% respectively. It is noticed that smaller the pore diameter, higher is the activity. In zeolite powder more surface area is available for binding of enzyme hence greater is the activity of pepsin. When the glutaraldehyde concentration is varied from 1 to 3% using 100 mesh for pepsin immobilised on egg shells, the activity was found to be 13, 40 and 20% respectively, of that of native enzyme. Thus the maximum activity was found to be with 2% glutaraldehyde concentration. Glutaraldehyde treatment for 2 h did not reduce the activity of the immobilised pepsin on 100 mesh egg shells, but a longer treatment caused a gradual decrease of about 40% after 8 h.

pH profile : The optimum pH for free and immobilised pepsin complexes were determined by using 1.6×10^{-3} M casein solution prepared in potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer of pH range 6.0–7.2. The optimum pH of the native enzyme and pepsin immobilised systems was found to be 6.4, the

immobilised complexes showing more activity at the extreme pH region compared to that of the native enzyme leading to broad pH curves.

Temperature profile : The maximum activity with both native and immobilised pepsin complexes was observed at an optimum temperature of 30° in 0.1 M potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer solutions of pH 6.4 (Fig. 1). No shift in optimum temperature occurred, which indicated that nature of carriers or mode of immobilisation has not drastically changed the morphology of the native enzyme.

Thermal stability : The denaturing tendency of the native pepsin was found to be greater when compared to the immobilised complexes (Fig. 1). It was observed that pepsin bound on egg shells retained 30% of activity even at 95° while the native pepsin was completely denatured at 65° only (Table 1). The substrate concentration has no effect on the thermal denaturation of pepsin. The pepsin bound to synthetic zeolites showed better thermal stability than the native enzyme. The pepsin immobilised on zeolites with pore diameter 5Å retained 17% of activity at 90°.

The thermal denaturation of immobilised complexes obey first order kinetics and suggests the type of binding of the enzyme to support⁹. It was suggested that bonding between enzyme and carrier zeolites loosely deformed to less stable immobilised enzyme complex than that which involves covalent binding

Fig. 1. Effect of temperature on pepsin catalysed hydrolysis of casein : (o) free pepsin, (Δ) Immb. on zeolites and (□) Immb. on egg shells.

as in case of enzyme immobilised on egg shells.

Substrate concentration : The activity of pepsin was studied by varying casein concentration from $(1.53 \text{ to } 15.3) \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ while keeping the other conditions constant. The reaction velocity increased upto $4.6 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$ of casein concentration and then remained constant.

Reusability : During this study, immobilised enzyme complexes were first used on casein for hydrolysis and the activity was noted. Then the immobilised enzymes were removed from the reaction contents and washed with buffer solution, dried and reused in the next batch reaction. It was observed that pepsin bound on egg shells was stable during repeated reuse without any substantial loss of activity compared to that in pepsin immobilised on synthetic zeolites. In the former case, enzyme is covalently linked to the carrier and in the latter case enzyme is physically adsorbed on the zeolites.

Kinetic and thermodynamic parameters : The enzymatic activity of both free and immobilised pepsin preparations with identical enzyme concentration were determined with substrate concentrations ranging from

TABLE 1—KINETIC AND THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Parameter	Pepsin		
	Free pepsin	Immb. on egg shell	Immb. on zeolite
Optimum pH	6.4	6.4	6.4
Optimum temperature (°C)	30	30	30
% Activity at 75°	00	45	17
K_m (10^4 mol dm^{-3}) at 283 K	1.05	1.81	1.04
K_m (10^4 mol dm^{-3}) at 303 K	0.98	1.56	0.985
V_{max} ($10^8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3} \text{ min}^{-1}$) at 303 K	10.0	7.57	7.93
E_a (kJ mol^{-1})	17.57	28.40	19.08
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1}) at 303 K	16.95	27.78	18.46
$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol^{-1}) at 303 K	114.9	125.0	115.5
$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ ($\text{JK}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$) at 303 K	323.0	320.0	320.0

1.6×10^{-5} to 1.6×10^{-4} M of pH 6.4 and incubated at temperatures 283, 293 and 303 K and Lineweaver-Burk plots were drawn. Taking 33500 as the molecular weight of pepsin¹⁰ and assuming all pepsin molecules on solid supports being dissolved homogeneously in reaction mixture without any limitation of inter- and intraparticle diffusion resistance, the values of K_m , V_{max} and other kinetic parameters were calculated (Table 1). No curvature was observed in the Lineweaver-Burk plots of immobilised preparations implying that the reactions were free of intraparticle diffusion resistance under the reaction conditions¹¹.

The almost negligible change in apparent K_m value of pepsin bound on zeolites from that of the native enzyme indicated that no charge-charge interactions were involved during the immobilisation of pepsin¹². Using the concept proposed by Mooyoung and Kobayaski¹³ that if relatively small amounts of enzyme are bound to carrier, the K_m apparent values of immobilised preparations approaches that of soluble enzyme, i.e. there will be not much loss of activity of enzyme on immobilisation. So relatively small amount of pepsin (10 mg) was bound to the larger amount of supports (5.0 g) and it was experimentally observed that apparent K_m values of both immobilised systems approached that of the free pepsin. Apparent K_m values of soluble as well as immobilised preparations are dependent of reaction temperature (Table 1). Such a temperature dependence can be explained from the fact that certain specific active groups are involved in Michaelis-Menten complex formation¹⁴. Relatively negligible change in Michaelis-Menten constant values of immobilised pepsins from that of soluble pepsin, suggests that the affinity of active groups of pepsin remains unaltered on immobilisation.

Comparative study of the kinetic parameters of both the pepsin immobilised systems indicates that the method of binding of pepsin on carrier egg shells and the zeolites has an influence on the magnitude of these kinetic parameters. The catalytic turnover V_{max} of pepsin bound on zeolites was higher than that of pepsin immobilised on egg shells, which indicates that no drastic changes in pepsin conformations was observed in the former case as seen in the latter case

The Arrhenius plots were drawn ($\log k$ vs $1/T$) and from the slopes, activation parameters were calculated (Table 1). Hike in activation energy of pepsin immobilised on egg shells indicates that enzyme is not freely available to the substrate as that in case of pepsin immobilised on zeolites because enzyme is firmly attached to the support egg shells unlike latter preparation.

Experimental

Pepsin immobilised on egg shells : The broken egg shell pieces were washed with boiling water, dried (60°), ground and sieved (100 mesh). The ground egg shell (4.9 g) was added to 0.1 M potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer (10 ml) of pH 6.4 containing pepsin (100 mg) and the mixture was stirred for 15 min. Then glutaraldehyde (0.2 ml) was added and stirred. The mixture was allowed to stand for 30 min. The bounded enzyme was centrifuged and washed thoroughly with phosphate buffer of pH 6.4.

Pepsin immobilised on synthetic zeolites Zeolite powder was washed with distilled water and dried at room temperature. Then 0.1 M potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer (10 ml) of pH 6.4 containing pepsin (100 mg) was added to previously weighed zeolites. The mixture was continuously stirred for 3 h, allowed to stand for 2 h, washed with buffer and stored at room temperature.

Method of assay : The activity of pepsin was determined using the method proposed by Anson with some modifications¹⁵. The method involved the estimation of hydrolysed products formed (TCA-soluble material) from casein.

A mixture of pepsin solution (10 mg/5.0 ml ; 1.0 ml) and with casein solution (2 mg in 100 ml 0.1 M potassium hydrogen phosphate buffer ; 5.0 ml) was incubated at 30° for 10 min. The reaction was terminated by addition of 20% trichloroacetic acid (2.0 ml). The precipitate formed was filtered after allowing it to stand for 15 min at room temperature. The concentration of hydrolysed products in the supernatant liq-

uid was determined by following the absorbance at 280 nm. The immobilised preparations were continuously agitated. The assay was highly reproducible even with immobilised preparations. The activity of pepsin was determined in a suitable aliquots by the reported procedure using tyrosine as the standard¹⁶. Under the conditions, the optical density of 1.00 corresponds to 82 μg of tyrosine released per min. when measured at 280 nm in a Hitachi spectrophotometer.

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